

Towards Inclusive Sustainability Pathways: Actor's Perspectives in the Mexican Octopus Fishery

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The octopus fishery in the Yucatán Peninsula is a vital source of livelihoods, food security, and cultural identity for local communities and also holds global significance, ranking amongst the top octopus producers worldwide. However, the Mexican octopus fishery faces multiple threats that put its long-term viability and sustainability at risk, including overexploitation, illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, climate change impacts, habitat degradation, inadequate governance and enforcement, among others. Understanding the complexities of small-scale fisheries and their sustainability challenges requires a systematic mapping of the value chain and the use of inclusive participatory approaches. This research provides a gender-sensitive update to the octopus value chain in the Yucatán Peninsula and identifies the factors that enable or undermine the sustainability of this important fishery. This study explores how different actors envision their roles and required resources—such as training, financial support, or organizational strengthening—in contributing to a more equitable and sustainable fishery. By including the local voices of several key actors—such as fishers, buyers, processors, middlemen, permit holders, scientists and others— we contribute to inclusive sustainability assessment frameworks in the context of small-scale fisheries, with the final aim to improve fisheries governance. Finally, we propose strategic and viable actions towards octopus fisheries sustainability.

